

Geologic map and landing site selection on Copernicus Crater (Moon)

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Copernicus Crater is a relatively young impact crater of ~800 Ma with a diameter of ~100 km and it is located on the lunar near side. Developed within the PlanMap project, we hereby present two geologic maps, at a broad and local scale, and the technical evaluation as a landing site with possible traverse paths and sampling sites. The scientific rationale guiding this study is that Copernicus is pivotal to refine the lunar time scale and because of its particular composition. Sample returns could provide absolute ages useful to improve both the lunar crater chronology and, by extrapolation, that of other inner solar system terrestrial bodies. Moreover, olivine spectral signature was detected (1), and this can provide information about the lunar crust and mantle. The whole central peak represents exhumed deep olivine-rich troctolite (1)

We performed a geologic mapping on the basis of the merged DEM of LOLA+Kaguya at 59 m of grid spacing and LROC WAC 100m/pixel mosaic. We also integrated spectral observations in order to recognize lithological variations and to better define the geologic units.

Cementine UVVIS color ratio mosaic was used: the band ratios combined in an RGB mosaic were used to determine the relative abundance in titanium, mafic minerals, and volcanic glasses.

In order to assess the possibility of landing in Copernicus we mapped in higher detail landforms that would be suitable as scientific stops in a rover traverse as well as to define possible obstacles and hazards, we produced a second geologic map at higher resolution (1:100.000) by means of a mosaic of LROC NAC images resampled at 5 m/pixel. The NW quadrant of Copernicus was chosen: it is the smoothest with relatively low number of obstacles and significant hazards. Three different landing ellipses were selected: sizes were derived from the NASA Mars rovers MSL Curiosity and Mars2020, since to date no constraints are available for the Moon. Hazards related to rock abundance was also investigated according to (2) within the landing ellipses as well as for small impact craters together with overall surface slope. Following the constraints defined for Schrödinger crater exploration in the HERACLES program (3) six traverses were defined: three long and three short traverses, of 32 and 16 km respectively. The sampling sites/stops for analyses were chosen to maximise the scientific return, following the future science goals in in situ lunar exploration (4).

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